

A REVIEW ON FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL TOOTHPASTE: A NATURAL APPROACH TO ORAL HYGIENE

Lakshmi Pandit¹, Annu Mahato¹, Sudha Kumari¹, Sushil kr. Mehta¹, Sourav Khawas^{*}

¹Jharkhand Rai University, Ranchi.

Article Received on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Revised on 25 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 05 January 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18150949>

*Corresponding Author

Sourav Khawas

Jharkhand Rai University, Ranchi.

How to cite this Article: Lakshmi Pandit, Annu Mahato, Sudha Kumari, Sushil kr. Mehta, Sourav Khawas^{*}. (2026). A Review on Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Toothpaste: A Natural Approach To Oral Hygiene. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(1), 628–636.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Herbal Toothpaste have become a popular alternative to conventional products, as many people believe that naturally ingredients are safer and had no side effect. They incorporate plant derived ingredient to maintain oral hygiene and prevent dental carries. Tooth decay is common in all ages but mainly affect in old ages people and children. Tooth decay is often caused by the demineralization of the enamel and dentin due to acid production by bacterial metabolism. This review assesses whether herbal toothpaste can offer improved oral hygiene prevent dental caries without the use of synthetics ingredients and evaluate its stability and overall effectiveness .Herbal toothpaste are generally preferred to be used as it contains natural ingredients that have no side effects. Formulation of

herbal toothpaste using different plant ingredients like guava leaves, neem twigs, sesame seeds, peppermint and tea tree oil, clove, Tulsi, babul etc, to prevent tooth decay and also used to remove yellow plaque. Plaque is a biofilm which causes tooth decay. The tooth paste using a variety of herbal component that have unique anti-bacterial and anti-inflammatory properties reduce dental caries (tooth decay) without using any chemical components and also evaluate its properties for stability and effectiveness. They improve periodontal health, reduce plaque accumulation, and help remove yellow plaque. Additionally, herbal toothpastes are generally well-accepted due to their pleasant natural flavours and absence of harsh chemicals, making them suitable for sensitive teeth and gums. Evaluation of these toothpaste formulations typically involves testing pH, spreadability, foamability, abrasiveness, stability, and antimicrobial activity, ensuring efficacy and consumer safety.

KEYWORDS: Herbal Toothpaste, Oral Hygiene, Anti-Bacterial, Anti-Inflammatory, Antimicrobial.

INTRODUCTION

India has a long tradition of using herbal toothpaste and this practice continues today due to increasing consumer preference for natural, safe and plant based oral care products. Herbal toothpaste contains natural ingredients, like polyphenol, alkaloids, and glycosides with proven biological activities.^[1] Toothpaste has been an essential part of oral care used since ancient times, with early formulation originating in China and India around 300-500 BC. Modern toothpaste evolved in the 19th century, with further advancements after 1945, including the use of sodium lauryl sulphate. It serves as dentifrice to clean the teeth, prevent plaque, and maintain oral health. Dental caries are mainly caused by *Streptococcus mutans*, remains a common global disease leading to tooth decay and pain. With growing concerns about side effects of synthetic agents, herbal and natural formulation are being explored as safer and effective alternatives for preventing dental caries and maintain oral hygiene.^[2,3] Herbal medicines derived from plants have long been used for healing with 80% of people worldwide relying on them for health care. Chronic gingivitis caused by plaque buildup, and can be prevented using effective ingredients with brushing. Neem is known for its antibacterial and anti-inflammatory properties helps to fight bacteria like *S. mutans* and prevents tooth decay.^[4] Dental caries affecting a large portion of the Indian population with a prevalence of 31.5% to 89%. It is a multifactorial infectious disease caused by factors such as cariogenic bacteria, fermentable carbohydrates, a susceptible host and time. Bacteria like *S. mutans* and *Lactobacillus acidophilus* play a key role by forming plaque biofilms and producing acids from carbohydrates leading to tooth demineralization and cavity formation. Plaque control involves mechanical cleaning chemical agents with antimicrobial activity. Poor oral hygiene is a common cause of plaque buildup and microbial growth in the mouth. Toothpaste often contains chemical like zinc fluoride, triclosan and copolyphosphate to reduce bacteria and prevent activities.^[5] Conventional toothpaste triclosan and fluoride having anti cariogenic properties bamboo salt, a traditional Korean herbal ingredient possesses anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and anti-oxidant properties. It is made by baking sea salt in bamboo tubes sealed with mud, which enriches it with minerals like Ca, K, Cu, Zn and makes it highly alkaline (pH 11.4). Toothpaste containing bamboo salt is believed to reduce plaque, gingivitis, tooth sensitivity and strengthen enamel.^[6] The microbes are the main cause of oral diseases, as they convert starchy foods into acids they damage teeth and gums leading to further health issues

like diabetes and heart diseases. Although chemical toothpaste containing fluoride, peroxide are effective as they possess health risks such as mouth irritation, dental stains and nausea. Researchers are developing herbal toothpaste using plant extracts from Aloe vera, neem, onion, tetraptera and other for their anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant properties.^[7] The cleaning of the teeth is performed by using toothbrush along with excipients used in toothpaste. The ingredients used in herbal toothpaste include abrasive, herbal extract binder, sweeteners preservatives, humectant, detergents, anti-oxidant and flavour. Fluoride containing toothpaste such as sodium F, mono-fluorophosphate or stannous fluoride can be harmful especially to children. Overexposure may cause health issues like red blood cell damage, neurological problems, headaches and reduced immunity and some toothpaste ingredients may also harm teeth and gums. Stevia leaves known for their therapeutic and antimicrobial properties, are explored as a natural safe alternative for toothpaste formulation.^[8]

HERBS USED IN FORMULATION OF HERBAL TOOTHPASTE.

HERBS	BIOLOGICAL SOURCE	FAMILY	ACTIVE CONSTITUENT	MEDICINAL USE
Neem	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Meliaceae	Azadirachtin Flavonoids Triterpenoids	Anti-itching Anti-bacterial Anti-microbial
Tulsi	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Lamiaceae	Eugenol Carvacol Methyl eugenol Ursolic acid Rosmarinic acid	Anti-viral Anti-malarial Anti-microbial
Cinnamon	<i>Cinnamomum zeylanicum</i>	Lauraceae	Eugenol Cinnamaldehyde Cinnamyl acetate Linalool	Anti-inflammatory Anti- diabetic Antioxidant Anti-microbial
Honey	<i>Apis mellifera Apis dorsata Apis florea</i> and other species of <i>Apis</i>	Apidae	Sugar Amino acid Minerals Fructose	Anti-bacterial Dry mouth Pain relief
Ginger	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Zingiberaceae	Gingerols Shogaols Paradol Zingerone	Antioxidant Anti-microbial Anti-nausea Anti-inflammatory
Clove oil	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	Myrtaceae	Eugenol Eugenyl acetate Beta caryophyllene	Antioxidant Anti-microbial Analgesic Pain relief
Palash	<i>Butea monosperma</i>	Fabaceae	Butein Quercetin Gallic acid	Analgesic Anti-inflammatory Anti- microbial
Karanj	<i>Millettia pinnata</i>	Fabaceae	Steric acid Oleic acid Flavonoids Alkaloids Terpenoids	Antioxidant Anti-microbial Anti-inflammatory
Miswak	<i>Salvadora persica</i>	Salvadoraceae	Silica Resin Sulfur Vitamin C	Astringent Anti-bacterial Anti-bacterial
Guava	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Myrtaceae	Carbohydrate Proteins	Anti-bacterial Antioxidant

			Fat Vitamin C	Anti-inflammatory
Brahmi	Bacopa monnieri	Scrophulariaceae	Saponins Alkaloids Bacosides	Anti-inflammatory Antioxidant

METHOD OF PREPARATION OF TOOTHPASTE

Trituration Method – The Trituration method is used when the base is liquid or semisolid and no heating is required. It is a process of grinding substance to a fine powder and then smoothly mixing them into a base.

Weigh all the ingredients accurately. Sieve the solid ingredients through a fine mesh to ensure fine particle size and uniform dispersion. Levigate the required amount of powder in a mortar with a small portion of the liquid or semi-solid base to form a smooth, thick paste. The levigating agent should be physically and chemically compatible with the other ingredients. Gradually add the rest of the base to the smooth paste, mixing thoroughly with a spatula or pestle until the mixture is uniform and the final paste is formed.^[2]

BENEFITS OF USING TRITURATION METHOD

- Particle size reduction
- Uniformly and homogeneity
- Improve adhesion and stability
- Enhancing therapeutic efficacy

DRAWBACK OF USING TRITURATION METHOD

- Moisture sensitivity
- Equipment wear
- Potential for contamination

DRY GUM METHOD

Accurately weigh all solid ingredients according to formula. Sieve the solids through sieve no 80 to ensure uniform particle size and remove lumps.^[9] Transfer the sieved solids to a mortar and pestle and mix thoroughly to obtain a uniform dry blend.^[10] Add the humectant slowly to the dry blend while triturating in the mortar and continue until a smooth semi-solid paste forms.^[11]

WET GUM METHOD

All the liquid components are mixed together to form a liquid phase. The binding agent is

then mixed with the liquid phase with uniform stirring to form mucilage. The solid ingredient except surfactant are added to the mucilage with uniform mixing in agitation mixer to form a homogenous paste. Now the surfactants, flavouring agent and colouring agent are added under vacuum to the paste.^[4,20]

Dry gum is the most commonly preferred method overall for herbal toothpaste because it is simple, robust for many excipients, and easy to scale from lab to small-industrial batches while maintaining good texture and stability.^[2] herbal toothpaste manufacturing describe dry gum as the standard cosmetic/toothpaste approach, with humectants and water gradually added to a dry solid mix, then surfactants and flavours under vacuum, which is compatible with common abrasives, binders and herbal actives.^[4,12]

In many herbal formulations the “dry gum method” is practically combined with trituration in a mortar and pestle, especially during base preparation and when incorporating herbal powders, to ensure uniform dispersion and smooth paste. Stand-alone trituration methods are popular at purely lab scale and give good results, but for routine or semi-industrial preparation, authors more often frame their process as dry gum with trituration rather than pure trituration or wet gum.^[13]

It is the dry gum method (usually with trituration steps) because it balances ease of processing, compatibility with standard toothpaste equipment, and consistent product quality.^[4]

COMPARITIVE ANALYSIS OF HERBAL & CHEMICAL TOOTHPASTE

Features	Herbal toothpaste	Chemical toothpaste
Ingredients used	Natural plant ingredients like neem, clove oil, tulsi, bamboo salt etc.	ic chemicals like SLS, CaCo ₃ , Silica, Fluoride etc.
Plaque and Gingivitis control	Herbal toothpastes are effective and achieve similar reduction in plaque and gingivitis.	Chemical toothpastes reduce plaque and gingivitis, fluoride not required for improving gingivitis.
Safety	Herbal toothpastes are safer than chemicals, and show good safety.	Chemical toothpastes meet safety standards, however some consumers prefer to avoid SLS, triclosan, or other synthetic preservatives.
Side effects	Herbal toothpastes may have fewer side effects because they rely on natural plant compounds rather than synthetic ones.	Chemical toothpastes have raised safety concerns in hormonal effects or have potential for resistance. Risks may vary depends on formulation.
Benefits	Combines anti-inflammatory, anti-	Prevent cavities using fluoride

bacterial and other properties from natural sources.	and provides stronger anti-microbial action
--	---

EVALUATION PARAMETERS OF TOOTHPASTE

1. Physical examination: The physical characteristics of herbal toothpaste—such as colour, aroma, taste, and texture—are visually and sensorially assessed. Smoothness is examined by rubbing between the fingers.^[14]

2. Homogeneity: By applying normal force at 270C, the toothpaste should extrude a homogeneous mass from the collapsible tube or other suitable container. Homogeneity is checked by extruding paste from the collapsible tube and observing consistency under normal conditions.^[15]

3. Determination of Sharp and Abrasive Particles: The paste was extruded about 15 to 20 cm length from collapsible tube of each sample on a butter paper. The test is conducted by rubbing a small quantity on butter paper or between fingers to detect any gritty sensation. Excessive abrasiveness can lead to dentin wear.^[16]

4. Foamability / Foaming Capacity: Foaming power is assessed by shaking a known amount of toothpaste with water in a graduated cylinder and measuring foam volume. A small amount of the toothpaste formulation was combined with water in a measuring cylinder, and the cylinder was shaken ten times to determine the foam ability of the toothpaste. The total amount of foam was recorded.^[12]

Determination of foaming power Foaming power = $V_1 - V_2$ Where,

V_1 - Volume in ml of foam with water. V_2 - Volume in ml of water only

5. Moisture Content / Loss on Drying (LOD): Excess water can cause separation or spoilage, while low moisture may harden the formulation. Required amount of sample to be taken in dish & drying is to done till constant weight. Loss of weight will indicate % loss of moisture & volatile matter. Moisture content impacts stability, microbial growth, and texture.^[17]

6. Microbial Load / Microbial Limit Test: The antimicrobial activity of the Toothpaste using of Bauer *et al* 24. The drug used in standard preparation was ofloxacin and ciprofloxacin of IP grade. The antimicrobial activity was performed by using 24hr culture of *S. Mutans* and *S. aureus*. There were 3 concentration used which are 25, 50 and 100mg/ml for each extracted phytochemicals in antibiogram studies.^[18]

7. Stability Studies: Stability tests ensure that colour, texturer, pH, and active herbal constituents remain unchanged over time. It was performed at different temperature for one month and studied for pH ,apperance and spreadability.^[19]

8. Spreadability: Spreadability is determined by testing how easily a 1-2 gram of sample spreads between two glass slides.

Formula was used to calculate spreadability: $S = M \times L / T$

Where,

S= Spreadability

M= Weight in the pan (tied to the upper slide) L= Length moved by the glass slide

T=Time (sec) taken to separate the upper slide from the ground slide.^[20]

9. Extrudability: The formulation has to be placed in a clean, collapsible plastic tube with a 5 mm nasal tip aperture. then the tube was squeezed with a finger. the amount of paste thar emerged from the tubes tip when pressure was applied was then used to gauge the tubes extrudibility.^[21]

10. pH determination: The pH was measured using calibrated pH meter. 1gm toothpaste placed in 100 ml of beaker. 10gm of distilled water, stir vigorously and make mixture.^[22]

11. Viscosity: The viscosity was determined using a Brookfield Viscometer using spindle no.3 by applying the increased values of shear rate to determine the flow behaviour of toothpaste. The viscosities measurements was performed at a temperature of 30 C.^[23]

CONCLUSION

Herbal toothpaste offers a promising natural alternative to conventional chemical-based formulations for maintaining oral hygiene and preventing dental issues such as caries and gingivitis. Formulated using plant-based ingredients like neem, tulsi, clove, ginger, and honey, these products demonstrate significant antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant capabilities. The formulation methods such as trituration method, dry gum and wet gum method are used and among them dry gum method are mostly preferred by industries for production at large scale. It is because this method give better dispersions and uniformity of solids, reduces air entrapment and compatible with large scale equipment. Herbal toothpaste can be effective, safe and consumer friendly for oral hygiene maintenance. Herbal toothpaste can match the quality of marketed toothpaste while providing an alternative to chemical

based oral care products. The evaluation parameters such as physical examination, pH determination, homogeneity, determination of sharp and abrasive particles, foamability, viscosity, moisture content, microbial test, stability test, spreadability and extrudibility. These parameters can collectively confirm that well formulated herbal toothpaste can achieve desirable physicochemical characteristics.

REFERENCE

1. Telrandhe R, Deshmukh P, Gunde M. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Toothpaste: Compared With Marketed Preparation. *Int J Pharm Drug Anal.*, 2017; 5(10): 406-410. doi:10.35629/7781-0502557560
2. Sahani S, Shirsath D, Gaikwad V. A Research on : Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Toothpaste. 2022; 9(12): 557-564.
3. Mangilal T, Ravikumar M. Preparation And Evaluation Of Herbal Toothpaste And Compared With Commercial Herbal Toothpastes: An Invitro Study. *Int J Ayurvedic Herb Med.*, 2016; 6: 2266-2251. <http://www.interscience.org.uk>
4. Khose AA. Herbal Toothpaste Formulation and Assessment: a Comprehensive Review. *Int Res J Mod Eng Technol Sci.*, 2023; (11): 3052-3061. doi:10.56726/irjmets46821
5. Kengadaran S, Anusha D, Baskar K, Muthukrishnan K, Pooraninagalakshmi J, Prabakar J. Comparative effectiveness of herbal and conventional toothpaste on prevention of dental caries: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Indian J Dent Res.*, 2022; 33(3): 332337. doi:10.4103/ijdr.ijdr_404_21
6. Biria M, Rezvani Y, roodgarian R, Rabbani A, Iranparvar P. Antibacterial effect of an herbal toothpaste containing Bamboo salt: a randomized double-blinded controlled clinical trial. *BMC Oral Health*, 2022; 22(1): 1-8. doi:10.1186/s12903-022-02224-z
7. Oluwasina OO, Idris SO, Ogidi CO, Igbe FO. Production of herbal toothpaste: Physical, organoleptic, phyto-compound, and antimicrobial properties. *Heliyon*. 2023; 9(3): e13892. doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e13892
8. Das K, Abdoolah TA, Sounder J. Formulation and evaluation of Stevia oral hygiene preparation: A noble herbal toothpaste. *Ann Phytomedicine An Int J.*, 2020; 9(1): 91-97. doi:10.21276/ap.2020.9.1.10
9. Nayak S, GD K., V, B P., S. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Toothpaste. *J Biol Sci Opin.*, 2024; 12(5): 54-59. doi:10.7897/2321-6328.12598
10. On AR, To T, Sensitive T. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2023; 12(9): 500-517. doi:10.20959/wjpr20239-28118

11. Senthilkumar KL, Venkateswaran. S, Vasanthan A, et al. Formulation development and evaluation of novel herbal toothpaste from natural source. *Int J Pharm Chem Anal.* 2022; 9(1): 17-21. doi:10.18231/j.ijpca.2022.003
12. Shingte BA, Pawar SM, Chavan PR, Malave KB. Formulation and Evaluation of Poly Herbal Toothpaste, 2024; 9(9): 517-528.
13. Kashte GM, Rajguru AG, Singh Solanki V. Formulation Development and Evaluation of Herbal Toothpaste by QBD. *Int J Pharm Res Appl.*, 2024; 9(2): 1894. doi:10.35629/4494090218941899
14. Shelke VR, Dhawale T. International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Toothpaste, 2024; 5(5): 13433-13439.
15. Wayal V, Mhaske S, Tribhuvan H. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Toothpaste. 2022; 2(5): 801-806. doi:10.48175/IJARSCT-4955
16. Sharma S, Agarwal SS, Prakash J, Pandey M, Singh A. Formulation Development and Quality Evaluation of Polyherbal Toothpaste "Oral S." *Int J Pharm Res Allied Sci.* 2014; 3(2): 30-39. www.ijpras.com
17. Journal A, Vol D, Shailendra W. No Title. 2016; 4(1): 1-5.
18. Shukla KV, Kumari D. Formulation Development and Evaluation of Herbal Toothpaste for Treatment of Oral Disease, 2019; 9: 98-104.
19. Ghurghure SM, Surwase PR, Pathan MA, Shirure PD. Design and Development of Tooth Paste Containing Alcoholic Extract of Psidium Guajava Leaf. *Am J PharmTech Res.* 2019; 9(2): 240-247. doi:10.46624/ajptr.2019.v9.i2.020
20. Deshmukh P, Telrandhe R. NATIONAL CONFERENCE : A Phytomedicine : A Novel Approach For Cancer Treatment Sponsered By Indian Council of Medical Research, Delhi. Organised By Kamla Nehru College Of Pharmacy, Butibori, Nagpur 441108, Maharastra, India. Formulation and Evaluat. Published online 2017; 1-9.
21. Kumar A, Yunus S, Ghatak A, Bhargava G, Kavitha PNKR. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL TOOTHPASTE. *WwwWjplsOrg* | . 2023; 10(10): 21-27. www.wjpls.org
22. Journal of Science and Healthcare Exploration (JSHE), Volume 2, Issue 2, Mar-Apr 2020, "Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Toothpaste" by Mr. Sable Kundan et al.28.pdf
23. Srivastava S, Biswal PK, Alam F, Anand A, Pal A. A review on toothpaste to treat sensitive teeth. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 2023; 12(9): 500-517. doi:10.20959/wjpr20239-28118.29.pdf